

CRUSH RESPONSE OF 2D AND 3D HYBRID WOVEN COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Failure, Hybrid, Shear*

1 General Introduction

Through-thickness response of materials is vital to understanding how a material will behave under impact or ballistic type loading. Quasi-static along with high rate testing must be performed to determine how these materials will behave to high rate impact and penetration events. Understanding the unique failure modes that are seen in during these events is very important to designing better materials for these applications.

Typical high strain rate testing includes the use of compressive Hopkinson bar setups. 2D in-plane woven material was investigated previously and found to form failure bands of high shear at angles to the loading direction under high rates of loading.^{1,2} Studies were further extended to 3D woven composites³ which showed similar shear band failure modes at high rates. It was also shown that at static rates vs. dynamic rates failure occurred differently in these materials with diffused microcracking at low rates and shear failure at high rates.⁴ Elevated rate tests show that a shear band typically formed in the material causing shear failure of the fiber tows. The angle of the band associated with shear failure has also been investigated previously to determine the effective failure envelope that can be formed.⁵

In this experimental investigation, static through-the-thickness mechanical properties of different types of 2D and 3D woven composites are determined through numerous different compressive test methods. One such modification to the through-the-thickness

compression tests is the confinement of one of the directions to prevent Poisson's effect from occurring. This additional confinement produces similar fracture to what is seen under ballistic loading conditions. The failure that is formed in the material produces a clear shear band which locally produces a combination of compressive and shear stresses, the results of which can be used to create a failure envelope that will help in understanding how these materials behave under various combinations of load.

2 Method

A standard compression test has been modified by adding confinement in one of the transverse directions. This prevents poisson's effect from happening. The fixture will cause a shear plane to form in the specimen. The failure surface looks like that seen in figure 1. The failure can then be broken down into normal and shear components through the use of Mohr's circle. These components can then be used to help understand the failure and predict the onset of failure in computational modeling.

Figure 1 Failure on surface of material

3 Materials

Many different materials were tested of 2D woven layups along with 3D Woven preforms. A configuration of pure glass along with hybrid configurations where carbon layers are added, and unsymmetric and symmetric configurations have been investigated. Samples were made using a VARTM process and were infused with SC-15 matrix material.

4 Results

Samples were tested and some values have been reported in table 1 showing the nominal stress. The results show that there is degradation in performance by adding the different layers of carbon to the material. The functionally graded material showed a further degradation in performance.

Table 1 Nominal Stress Values

	Nominal Stress (ksi)	Standard Deviation (ksi)	Nominal Values
3D Glass	93	3.9	1
3D UnSymmetric	79.1	4.4	0.85
3D Symmetric	84.4	1.9	0.91
Functionally Graded	66.6	4.2	0.72

The samples were then examined and the failure angles were measured to determine effective components in the material systems. Table 2 shows the effective angles along with the nominal stress and shear stress associated for each of the configurations. The functionally graded material never failed with a shear band, therefore these values can not be reported. The carbon layers did not show clear shear banding, rather it was confined to the glass layers in the material. 2D preforms are still undergoing testing.

Table 2 Component Stress Values

	Shear Angle (deg)	Normal Stress (ksi)	Shear Stress (ksi)
3D Glass	37.5	66	41
3D UnSymmetric	45.3	39	39
3D Symmetric	39	51	41
Functionally Graded	N/A	N/A	N/A

5 Conclusions

Through-the-thickness confined compression test results revealed some interesting trends in the failure mode of hybridized 3D woven composites. The hybridized fiber architectures show significant effect on the measured nominal failure response of these materials. In the symmetric and unsymmetric hybrid materials we get similar failure modes all occurring in the glass layer which is the weakest layer from individual testing. The functionally graded material does not have a clear transition in materials, rather each layer has mixture of tow (carbon and glass) that the interaction of those tows has localized the fiber/matrix failure, and preventing the formation of a major shear band.

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